

Viewers' Perception of the Impact of Nollywood Films on the Projection of Nigerian Cultural Values

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20318843>

Abstract

Nollywood, the Nigerian film industry, has witnessed tremendous growth from past decades till the present day and has been able to carve out its niche on different social media platforms. This potentially places the country's indigenous cultures in the spotlight and, as a result, causes concern. This study seeks to ascertain the prospects and challenges associated with Nollywood film productions and to further examine how viewers perceive the industry's projection of Nigeria's cultural values. The research, which was anchored on issue framing theory, was targeted at 291 respondents in Anambra State using questionnaire as instrument of data collection. Findings revealed that Nollywood films have grossly contributed to the growth of the entertainment industry and also popularised some indigenous cultures; that the industry is flawed by steady repetition of storylines and poor technical quality of its productions, and that Nollywood films often project more of diabolical money ritual films and also misinterpret some cultural practices, thereby painting negative pictures of Nigerian culture to its viewers. Consequently, it was recommended that Nollywood productions should focus more on the portrayal of the rich Nigerian cultural values rather than past or unverifiable negative cultural practices that have no place in the current Nigerian society and that scriptwriters should always contact village and traditional heads to get facts that will reflect the true version of any aspect of culture they want to project before writing and producing.

Keywords: Cultural Values, Film production, Issue Framing Theory, Nollywood, Viewers' Perception

Introduction

Film is one of the significant tools of communication available to human society. According to Asogwa, Onoja & Unekwu (2015), earlier research and empirical evidence have established the fact that film could serve as a tool for mass socialisation, information, education and national development in general. It is a means of communication and comprehension of people's diverse cultural values. Ogbe, Ayodele, Onyeka & William (2020, p. 119) state that "in Nigeria, the Nollywood, which is the household name for the movie industry in Nigeria, can be described as a potential tool for the promotion of cultural identity and national development." In other words, the industry

has, over time, given the diverse Nigerian cultures identification in the international arena.

The introduction of films and cinemas into Nigeria ushered in an important era in the history of mass communication in this country. Udomisor & Sonuga (2012) state that through films and videos, the cultural background and identity of a nation are exhibited to the outside world. Films and videos have become vital media used to exhibit, popularise and project the cultures of Nigeria to the outside world. This also becomes more interesting with a country like Nigeria, which is multi-ethnic and thus has a wide variety of indigenous cultures to promote.

Films have the potential to be the most powerful form of public communication, which is why they are so popular. It is not only a low-cost source of entertainment for the people, but it also has the potential to become a method of mass education and mass teaching. According to Omoera (2012), the video-film medium has established itself firmly as a permanent fixture in the Nigerian culture and entertainment sector, as well as in the entertainment industry as a whole throughout the world. People are encouraged to adopt new patterns of lifestyle, fashion, and so on as a result of the persuasive power of the mass media, which has a significant impact on people's beliefs and behaviours. Films, more than any other kind of media, have a significant amount of influence on the way people think in society (Ezegwu, Okechukwu & Etukudo, 2016).

Nigerian home videos have been used to exhibit the desirable aspects of the country's culture internally and across the country. According to Udomisor & Sonuga (2012, p. 28), "the films are exported to propagate our norms, values and traditions". They are meant to educate, socialise and play a therapeutic role in the entertainment function of the mass media. Nevertheless, there have been issues of concern over the role of Nigerian films and videos and the image that they have portrayed of Nigerian culture. This study, therefore, seeks to make an assessment of the depiction of Nigerian culture by the Nollywood film industry; to deduce if there is a fair representation or, on the other hand, a poor imitation of what is obtainable in the Nigerian culture.

Statement of the Problem

Nollywood, the film industry in Nigeria, has undoubtedly grown popular among the Nigerian audience, most parts of Africa and the world at large. The sustainability of this popularity vis-à-vis the promotion of what is generally accepted as the way of life of Nigerians has become an issue among film patrons and the likes in society. In the era of globalisation, which is considered a playing ground for competitiveness of qualitative cultural products, films, as such a product, ought to be qualitative enough in order to positively place Nigerian cultures in the global sphere (Effiong, 2018). However, there are some major concerns about the way and manner in which the films and video media are used to portray Nigerian cultures to the outside world. It is in view of the above that this study takes a cursory view of Nollywood's projection of Nigerian cultural values to the film viewers across the globe believing that whatever is projected about Nigeria by the Nigerian film industry as a window to the world, has an agendum setting effect on foreign audience and could help correct some of the misconceptions about Nigerians and

their rich cultural values. The study, therefore, seeks to find out Viewers' Perception of the Impact of Nollywood Films on the Projection of Nigerian Cultural Values

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study were to:

1. Find out the most significant prospects associated with Nollywood film productions.
2. Identify the most significant challenges associated with Nollywood film productions.
3. Examine how Nollywood projects Nigerian cultural values to its potential viewers.

Growth and Development of the Nigerian Film Industry: A Historical Perspective

Nigerian audiences' first experience in film screening was on August 12, 1903, at the Clover Memorial Hall in Lagos (Uchegbu 1992, p. 48). Even though film was introduced by a European merchant, it took the combined efforts of the colonial administration and the church to sustain the industry (Ekwuazi, 1987, p. 1). During this time, film was also used as a tool for education, as evidenced in the screening of educational documentaries ranging from agriculture, healthcare and other important issues through the mobile free cinemas that would tour Nigerian villages (Udomisor & Sonuga, 2012). The British colonialists used it for their "civilising" mission as well as to indicate the blessedness of being colonised.

Notably, the Nigerian film, as established by Udomisor & Sonuga (2012), has expanded and grown in leaps and bounds and has become the third most popular and largest producer after Hollywood of the United States and Bollywood of India. Adesanya (1997, p. 15) notes that the cost of production greatly hampered film production. Filmmakers unable to cope with the cost of shooting on celluloid first turned to reversal film stock and later on, videotapes. So unlike the American and Indian film industry, the Nigerian film industry, popularly called Nollywood, uses the video cassette format and recently the Video Compact Disc (VCD). As a consequence, the films are not shown in Cinema houses since they are shot straight onto video tapes, replicated and sold for home viewing, hence the term home videos.

Nollywood films are popular in Nigeria because they have indigenous content and address issues relevant and relative to the mass audience/viewers. "Through an amalgamation of Nigerian narrative techniques (African storylines) and Western technology, these films document and re-create socio-political and cultural events that occurred within and beyond the country's borders" (Udomisor & Sonuga, 2012, p. 28). Video films are not only popular in native Nigeria and other African countries, but in less than twenty years, they have attracted the attention of many media practitioners, film festivals like Cannes, and some American and European universities. In fact, DSTV (Digital Satellite Television), a digital satellite service in Africa, features "Africa Magic" (Channels 151, 152, 153, 154, 156, 157 and 159), as well as ROK, ROK 2 and ROK GH,

which are shown on Channels 168, 169 and 164 respectively. These are channels devoted to Nollywood films and movies from other West African countries.

Nigerian People and Culture

Culture is as old as humanity and traceable to the beginning of man's existence. It could be seen as a way of life of a people or a reason for the existence of a people, etc. (Akpor, Omoruyi & Uyeri, 2019). *Penguin English Dictionary* cited in Opubor, Nwuneli & Oreh (1979, p. 31) defines culture as an "improvement of mental faculties, refined taste or judgments, high intellectuals, and aesthetic development of a group characterised by a special level of material achievement". Culture is a way of life which a people have fashioned for themselves. According to Akpor *et al* (2019), it includes their art, their science and all their social transition, including their belief systems and rituals.

The idea of culture should not be limited to just Music, Dance, Drama, and the arts. According to Akpor, *et al* (2019, p. 405), "it is the intertwining of the artistic fibers of a nation, with the science and religion of its people, the law and moral expectations of the community, the wisdom of their past and the education of their present and future". Opubor, *et al* (1979, p. 31) further define culture as "a vast apparatus, partly material, partly human and partly spiritual by which societies are organised into permanent and recognisable groups". It has gone beyond idol worshipping since whenever its concept is discussed what readily comes to the mind of an average African is "the picture of his forebears dancing around giant trees in sacrificial worship or otherwise the picture of a Sango man casting spells and mouthing incantations in the process of some unholy ritual" (Ibanga, 1993, p. 3).

The culture of an individual is dependent on the culture of the society, and or the society to which that individual belongs. What this assertion means, according to Elliot cited in Enahoro (2009, p. 19), is that an individual is shaped by his or her culture...and finds that being part of the culture club provides ethical security. Culture influences individuals in society; it directs their pattern of thinking and behaviours to what it wants them to do. Culture is not limited to music, dance, the law and the moral expectations of the community, the wisdom of their past and the education of the present and the future (Akpor *et al* 2019).

Assessment of Thematic Issues in Nollywood Films

One of the major criticisms of Nollywood films is obsession with the occult world (juju, black magic, sorcery, ritual murder, and witchcraft), obscenity, prostitution, kidnapping and "money worship" (Udomisor & Sonuga, 2012). Nigerian video films, along with their Ghanaian counterparts, have been described by Larkin (2005) as a mixture of "horror, magic and melodrama." There is nothing wrong with a film dealing with any of these themes, but critics frown at the fact that they recur, film after film. The industry seems beset with a seen-one-seen-them-all syndrome. Producers may argue that video films address the social problems plaguing society, yet many people are disturbed by their treatment of ethical and moral issues.

Another notable issue in Nollywood films is the representation of women. Okome, a respected film academic and promoter of the Nigerian video film, has on occasions spoken on aspects of the representation and “objectification” of women in Nigerian movies. According to Anyanwu (1987), the impression is that women are negatively portrayed to appeal to the male-dominated audience. In some films, women are portrayed as prostitutes, wily lovers, and witches and all manner of imaginable criminality. According to Udomisor & Sonuga (2012), some films are gender insensitive, and many still abide by the traditional and conservative attitude toward women.

The difference is that the rituals and murders, which occur in Southern films, have not yet appeared in Northern movies. Still, women in the Northern films are not reflected any better; as they are shown/seen as greedy, fickle-minded, weak, unable to make their own marital decisions and are available for purchase by the highest bidder (Anyanwu 84-85). Nigerian movies perpetuate sex role stereotypes and reflect the patriarchal social values dominant in Nigerian society, which amounts to what Tuckman calls the “symbolic obliteration of women”.

Representation of Nigerian Indigenous Culture in Nollywood

According to Asogwa *et al* (2015), the Nollywood film industry remains the dominant film industry in Africa that is poised to champion the projection of the Nigerian cultural values through film. Ibie (2004), in Asogwa, *et al* (2015, p. 98), the development of Nollywood dates back to the colonial era, through the efforts of the European merchant, colonial administration and the church. The first film screening experience in Nigeria was on August 12, 1903, at the Clover Memorial Hall in Lagos (Uchegbu, 1992). The industry that started like a joke now ranks and competes with Hollywood and Bollywood, in terms of quantity (Fafiolu, 2014); locally outsells foreign ones and is also appreciated all over the world (Akpabio, 2007).

The success in home video productions and the corresponding audience interest have attracted a lot of attention to the film sector. According to Udomisor & Sonuga (2012, p. 28), “there is no newspaper or magazine in Nigeria that does not allocate space to this singularity.” So many articles have been written on the quality and beauty of home video productions. Most of the comments on video films have always been emphasised on sex, violence, fetishism, occultism, voodoo and other negative issues (Udomisor & Sonuga, 2012, p. 28). In the same vein, the production quality of these films has also been severely criticised. In spite of all these criticisms, new home video films are released regularly into the Nigerian market.

Notably, additional evils have deeply penetrated the fabric of Nigerian society. The high level of corruption in Nigeria and the “hero” worship and recognition accorded the “wealthy” have conveyed the false idea to many youths that becoming rich through whatever means is the only way to be relevant (Udomisor & Sonuga, 2012). The killing of humans by cultists has therefore become rampant in contemporary Nigeria. Some Nollywood films generally portray the culture of idolising questionable or illicit wealth, a culture involving many Nigerian youths, as unacceptable.

Related Empirical Studies

Ewomazino, Omoruyi & Uyaeri (2019) conducted a study that sought to find out whether the themes of Nollywood films portray Nigerian indigenous cultural values in true light or not. The study concludes that Nigerian films started well by promoting our rich cultural heritage, but somewhere along the line deviated to accommodate financial gains. This became prominent when the viewers of Nollywood videos increased drastically, thereby giving rise to competition among film producers who were ready to pay heavily to get stories that would move and increase sales. The work recommends that the Nigerian film censors' commission should scrutinise films before they are sent out for viewing by the larger audience, and that script writers should always have at the back of their minds that Nigeria's cultural heritage should be foremost on their minds when they are writing any script.

Chika, Ibe & Ojih (2015) conducted research which sought to find out how Nollywood projects Nigerian rich local cultural values to the outside world. The study observes, among others, that Nollywood dwells too much on the negative aspect of the nation's cultural practices to the detriment of the nation's image. Udomisor & Sonuga (2012) examined how films and home videos produced in Nigeria had fared in delivering and propagating the norms and values of Nigerians to the outside world. The study found that some local and international critics see Nigeria's film industry as a poor imitation of the real thing, as productions are plagued by technical glitches. The study also found that despite the international attention received by Nollywood films, the quality of its productions and the content of its stories are issues that need to be seriously worked on.

Ezegwu, Okechukwu & Owo (2016) carried out research that focused on the representation of witchcraft and voodoo in films. According to the findings of the research, filmmakers in Nollywood are driven by financial gain to create films with witchcraft-related themes. According to the findings of the research, directors working in Nollywood should always prioritise matters of national concern above those of others and should choose to depict topics that represent Nigeria's socio-cultural values, ideas, beliefs, and attitudes.

Theoretical Framework

Issue Framing Theory

The basis of framing theory is that the media focus attention on certain events and then place them within a field of meaning. The theory assumes that the media draws the public's attention to certain topics, it decides what people think about, the topic the journalist selects. Thus, as noted by Asemah (2011), a frame refers to the way media and media gatekeepers organise and present the events and issues they cover and the way audiences interpret what they are provided. Baran & Davis (2009, p. 35) explain further that the framing theory examines the idea of how people use expectations to make sense of everyday life. The basis of framing theory is that the media focus attention on certain events and then place them within a field of meaning. This field of meaning can have an effect on the audience's beliefs, attitudes and behaviours, by connecting a particular

meaning or interpretation of an issue. The Nigerian Nollywood film industry often centres the themes of its productions on the Nigerian cultural values. It is pertinent to note that the way these cultures are presented, whether negative or positive, in films will determine the impression that viewers (foreign ones especially) will have about the Nigerian culture.

Methodology

The survey research method was adopted for this study. This method seeks to study people across different demographic and psychographic diversities. Gyuse (2005) notes that the survey method focuses on facts about people and their beliefs, opinions, attitudes, motivations and behaviours. Emaikwu (2006) also asserts that the survey research method is one in which a group of people or items are studied by collecting and analysing data from only a few people considered to be a representative of the entire population. The populations for this study are viewers of Nollywood films in Anambra State. However, the researcher purposively selected 300 respondents as the sample size and further stratified them into the 3 senatorial zones of the state, namely: Anambra North, Central and South Senatorial zones. Subsequently, 100 copies of the questionnaire were allotted to each of the senatorial zones. Primary and secondary sources of data collection were used in this study, while simple statistics were used for data analysis.

The total number of copies of the questionnaire distributed was 300, but only 291 were valid and used for data analysis. The remaining 9 copies were not appropriately filled and thus were not used. Consequently, a total of 388 copies of the questionnaire were used for data analysis.

The collected data on the gender of the respondents show that 142 respondents (48.8%) indicated that they were males, while 149 respondents (51.2%) were females, implying that both sexes were fairly represented. In their age brackets, 65 respondents (22.3%) fell within the age range of 18-25 years, 86 respondents (29.6%) ranged from 26-35 years, 76 respondents (26.1%) were within the range of 36-45 years, while 64 respondents (22%) ranged from 46 years and above. The occupational status of the respondents indicated 94 respondents (32.6%) were civil servants, 76 respondents (26.4%) were traders, 97 respondents (33.7%) were students, while 21 respondents (7.3%) were farmers. Thus, in terms of age and occupation, the respondents were mature and independent.

Data Analysis and Presentation

Table 1: Prospects associated with Nollywood Film Productions

Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Popularises indigenous culture	94	32.3%
Revives forgotten cultural practices	24	8.2%
Provides high entertainment value	45	15.5%
Tool for cultural preservation	30	10.3%
Contributes to the growth of the entertainment industry	98	33.7%
Total	291	100%

Table 1 presents a distribution of respondents according to the most significant prospects associated with Nollywood film productions. From the responses on the table, 94 respondents (32.3%) indicated that it popularises indigenous culture, 24 respondents (8.2%) indicated that it revives forgotten cultural practices, 45 respondents (15.5%) indicated that it provides high entertainment value, 30 respondents (10.3%) indicated that it serves as a tool for cultural promotion, while 98 respondents (33.7%) indicated that it contributes to the growth of the entertainment industry.

Table 2: Challenges associated with Nollywood Film Productions

Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Poor funding of productions	32	11%
Poor technical quality	92	31.6%
Poor storylines	42	14.4%
Repetition of storylines	96	33%
Rising spate of unprofessionalism	29	10%
Total	291	100%

Table 2 presents a distribution of respondents according to the most significant challenges associated with Nollywood film productions. As seen from the table, 32 respondents (11%) mentioned poor funding, 92 respondents (31.6%) indicated that it was poor technical quality, 42 respondents (14.4%) indicated that it was poor storylines, 96 respondents (33%) indicated that it was repetition of story lines, while 29 respondents (10%) indicated that it was the rising spate of unprofessionalism in the industry.

Table 3: How Nollywood Films largely portray the Nigerian Culture

Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Positive	92	31.6%
Negative	199	68.4%
Total	291	100%

Table 3 presents a distribution of respondents according to how Nollywood films largely portray the Nigerian culture. 92 respondents (31.6%) indicated that it portrayed it in a positive light, while 199 respondents (68.4%) indicated that Nigerian cultural values have been largely portrayed in a negative light by Nollywood films.

Table 4: Specificity of what Nollywood often project about the Nigerian Cultural Values

Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Projection of histories and documentaries	30	10.3%
Projection of rich existing cultural values	16	5.5%
Projection of diabolical money ritual stories	101	34.7%
Projection of misinterpreted cultural practices	96	33%
Projection of voodoo and black magic	48	16.5%
Total	291	100%

Table 4 presents a distribution of respondents according to their specification of what Nollywood films often project about the Nigerian culture in their productions. From the responses on the table, (10.3%) indicated that it projects more of histories and documentaries, 16 (5.5%) indicated that it projects more of rich existing cultural values, 101 (34.75%) indicated that it projects more of diabolic money ritual stories, 96 (33%) indicated that it projects more of misinterpreted cultural practices, while 48 (16.5%) indicated that Nollywood films project more of voodoo and black magic in their films.

Discussion of Findings

This study aimed to evaluate viewers' perceptions of the impact of Nollywood films on the projection of Nigerian cultural values. Three research questions were raised, and three major findings were made. The first finding established that there were prospects associated with Nollywood film productions, which include: its contribution to the growth of the entertainment industry, as well as its popularisation of indigenous culture. This finding corroborates the views of Asogwa *et al* (2015), who note that the Nollywood film industry remains the dominant film industry in Africa that is poised to champion the projection of the Nigerian cultural values through film. Fafiolu (2014) observes that the industry that started like a joke now ranks and competes with Hollywood and Bollywood, in terms of quantity; while Akpabio (2007) establishes that locally outsell foreign ones and are also appreciated all over the world.

The study also found that certain challenges are most significantly associated with the Nollywood, and these include steady repetition of storylines, as well as the poor technical quality of their productions. Other findings revealed that the Nollywood film industry often portrayed Nigeria's culture in a negative light, which is evident from the fact that they projected more diabolical money ritual stories and also projected misinterpretations of the Nigerian culture. By so doing, the Nollywood regulate its other social responsibility of being a tool for conveying the nation's cultural heritage to its national and foreign audiences, according to Aliede (2011).

Udomisor & Sonuga (2012) share similar opinions when they opine that one of the major criticisms of Nollywood films is obsession with the occult world (juju, black magic, sorcery, ritual murder, and witchcraft), obscenity, prostitution, kidnapping and "money worship". Chika, Ibe & Ojih (2015) similarly observe that Nollywood dwells too much on the negative aspect of the nation's cultural practices to the detriment of the nation's image, while Udomisor & Sonuga (2012) find out that some local and international critics see Nigeria film industry as a poor imitation of the real thing, as productions are plagued by technical glitches. The above finding validates the significance of the issue framing theory to this study. This is because the erroneous depiction of the Nigerian culture by most Nollywood productions will relatively create a dark, poor image of its richness and true values, especially in the international arena.

Conclusion

The Nollywood industry has continued to grow from strength to strength over the years and has successfully given much projection to the nation's indigenous culture.

Notwithstanding, film production in the industry is being gradually marred by certain loopholes, some of which include: its poor technical quality in terms of production and its steady repetition of certain storylines, even amidst other realities about the nation that could be showcased to the world. More worrisome is the fact that Nollywood's repetition of storylines has shown not only that the industry lacks adequate proficiency and professionalism, but also deviates from cultural promotion, thereby projecting more of diabolical contents about Nigeria and painting false images of the reality of the Nigerian culture, undoubtedly inimical to the positive portrayal of the good image and reputation of the country culturally or diplomatically.

Recommendations

Given these salient and pending issues, the study recommends the following:

1. Nollywood productions should focus more on the portrayal of the rich cultural Nigerian values rather than projecting past or unverifiable negative cultural practices that have no place in the current Nigerian society anymore.
2. The Nigerian Films and Video Censors' Board should thoroughly scrutinise films before they are sent out for viewing by the larger audience. In the same way, script writers should always have at the back of their minds that Nigerian cultural heritage should be foremost on their minds when they are writing any script and that village or traditional heads should be contacted to get actual story lines that would reflect their culture.
3. In a bid to stay afloat, especially with the rising spate of technological innovations, film producers should brace up with the technical quality of their productions, just like Hollywood films.
4. Members of the Nigerian film industry should patiently undergo thorough education, training and orientation to acquire the necessary rudiments of filmmaking and production, rather than rushing to churn out many films/videos within a short time, which is responsible for the current apparent mess of the industry.

References

- Adesanya, A. (1997). From film to video. In Haynes, J. (ed.), *Nigerian Video Films*. Lagos: Kraft Books Limited.
- Akpabio, E. (2007). Attitude of audience members to Nollywood films, *Nordic Journal of African Studies*, 16(1), 90-100.
- Akpor, E. D., Omoruyi, J. & Uyeri, S. O. (2019). Nollywood films and the promotion of cultural values in Nigeria. *International Journal of Social Science and Economic Research*, 4(1), 44-62.
- Aliede, J. E. (2011). Strengthening the operational capacities of the mass media for effective contributions to rebranding Nigeria. *Public Relations Journal*. 7 (1), 1-18.

- Anyanwu, C. (2003). Towards a new image of women in Nigerian video films. In: Ogunleye F, editor. *African Video Film Today*. Manzini, Swaziland: Academic Publishers.
- Asemah, E. S. (2011). *Principles and practice of mass communication*. Jos: Great Future Press.
- Asogwa, C. E., Onoja, I. B. & Unekwu, O. E. (2015). The representation of Nigerian indigenous culture in Nollywood. *Journal of Scientific Research and Reports (JSRR)*, 7(2), 97-107.
- Baran, S. J. & Davis, D. K (2009). *Mass communication theory: Foundations, format and future* (5th Ed). Boston: Wadsworth Cengage Learning.
- Effiong, C. (2018). Dynamics of globalisation and multiculturalism for the sustenance of Nollywood. *Journal of Globalisation Studies*, 9(2), 110-125.
- Ekwuazi, H. (1987). *Film in Nigeria*. Ibadan: Moonlight Publishers.
- Emaikwu, O. S. (2006). *Fundamentals of educational research methods in statistics*. Lagos: Deray Prints Ltd.
- Enahoro A. (1989). Filmmakers and filmmaking in Nigeria: Problems and prospects. *Africa Media Review*, 13(3), 98-109.
- Ezegwu, D. T., Okechukwu, N. C. & Etukudo, O. R. (2016). The effect of the portrayal of witchcraft/voodoo in Nollywood on Nigeria's national development. *Oko Journal of Communication and Information Science (OJCIS)*. 2(1), 1-18.
- Fafiolu, G. O. (2014). Nollywood: A viable vehicle of public diplomacy in Nigeria. *New Media and Mass Communications*, 11, 21-25.
- Gyuse, T. T. (2005). *How to plan, execute and report your research*. Makurdi: Selfers Educational Books.
- Ibie, N. (2004). How video films developed in Nigeria. Retrieved from <http://www.nollywood.net>.
- Larkin, B. (2005). Video Awodjo: Popular Video Film in the AFF/NY 2001 Festival. 11 Sept.
- Ogbe, S. J., Ayodele, B. J., Onyeka, E. D. & William, Y. (2020). Film as a purveyor of Nigeria's image and socio-cultural development: an analysis of selected Nollywood Movies. *African Journal of Arts and Humanities*, 6(6), 119-139.
- Omoera, O. S. (2012). The Benin Language Video-Film in Nollywood: A Cultural Round of Engagement. A Paper Presented in a Post-Graduate Seminar, Department of Theatre Arts, University of Ibadan, August 17, 2012.
- Opubor A., Nwuneli, O. E. & Oreh, O. (1979). 'The status, role and future of the film industry in Nigeria' in A. Opubor and O.E. Nwuneli (eds.) *The Development and Growth of the Film Industry in Nigeria*. Lagos: National Council for Arts and Culture.
- Uchegbu, B. (1992). Goal-oriented film censorship policy for Nigeria: lessons from the colonial era. In Ekwuazi, H. and Nasidi, Y. (eds.), *Operative Principles of the Film Industry: Towards a Film Policy for Nigeria*. Jos: Nigerian Film Corporation.
- Udomisor, I. & Sonuga, A. (2012). Content analysis of programs produced by Nollywood, particularly on Africa Magic: DSTV. *Research on Humanities and Social Sciences*, 2(11), pp. 27-34.